

Research programme to share knowledge and improve uptake of new digital technologies in sheep and goat farming

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101000471.

INNOVATIONS ON SMALL RUMINANT FARMS

Sm@RT POLICY BRIEFS

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

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Introduction

General introduction about the project

Sm@RT (Small Ruminant technologies –Precision Livestock Farming & Digital technologies for small ruminants) is a European network to share experience of new technologies for sheep and goats. It brings together a network of researchers, farmers and advisors to improve awareness of innovative tools, demonstrating their potential and possible return on investment.

Sm@RT involved 11 partners in 8 countries, and focus on dairy goats, dairy sheep and meat sheep farmers.

Sm@RT fostered exchanges on technologies between farmers during farm demonstration days on innovative farms and digifarms.

Sm@RT created resources for farmers regarding available technologies, to progress in their digitization process to meet their needs and objectives. Guidelines, cost-benefit analysis, farmers' testimonies and videos have been created to encourage uptake of solutions to needs.

Findings

In general, the findings of this project confirm that:

- Although only 15 % of farmers surveyed have technologies on their farms, 79% of them would like to use technologies to help with feeding/grazing, health and welfare, reproduction, flock/herd management, fattening and/or milking
- A total of 166 ranked needs were identified and 60 innovative technology solutions were proposed to the farmers.
- Training sessions on Digifarms and Farm Demonstration on Innovative farms proved an ideal medium for peer-to-peer knowledge transfer regarding the use of technologies.
- The main barriers to uptake are linked to costs of technologies, but also to the lack of training options, after-sales advice, confidence in one's skills and compatibility between the devices.
- Sharing of knowledge and experiences between farmers, researchers and other stakeholders in different countries proved invaluable.
- There is a lot of information regarding cost of technologies, but the information is often dispersed and not always in a format (or language) easy to understand or to adapt to one's farming situation. Cost-benefit analyses are necessary for farmers to fully decide on investing in technologies or not.

The project identified 4 key messages, that are developed in policy briefs:

1. Focus on research needs
2. Peer-to-peer demonstration & training needs for farmers
3. Innovations on small ruminant farms
4. Adoption & uptake of innovative technologies

This policy brief focus on key message #3 – Innovations on small ruminant farms

*The recommendations identified in the four policy briefs have been developed during the life of the project by the partners and in collaboration with **over 1350** stakeholders during the project's participatory workshops.*

*The project carried out an initial online survey to capture farmers' opinions, which gathered **over 660** answers. A total of **52** national workshops have been conducted, together with **five** transnational workshops, **one** final seminar and **one** international visit. **Over 635** individual farmers' evaluations have been collected during **30** training sessions and farm demonstrations days on Digifarms and Innovative Farms.*

Recommendations at a glance

- ✓ **Global surveys are useful to provide an overview of technology uptake across the small ruminant industries.**
- ✓ **Information collected associated with barriers to uptake indicate the need for training & after sales support.**
- ✓ **Financial support would also help to encourage more innovation on farms.**
- ✓ **Implementing tools & technologies can provide several different benefits.**
- ✓ **Detailed cost-benefit analyses of the innovative technologies, including scale of the business, are needed**

What is the challenge?

- There is a lack of uptake of innovative technologies by sheep and goat farmers in Europe and beyond.
- Common misconception is that there are not many tools and technologies relevant to small ruminant farms.
- Of small ruminant farms that do have innovation, there is very little knowledge as to what the tools and technologies are currently being used for and why.
- There is a need to highlight the different tools & technologies available and provide guidance to farmers in terms of how to use them, the potential costs involved and the likely benefits.

What did we learn from Sm@RT?

- Across the Sm@RT Digifarms & Innovative Farms, a wide range of tools and technologies are being used.
- Benefits seen included = easier to collect data, better flock/herd management, time/labour saving & improved welfare.
- An online survey, carried out by Sm@RT, was designed to collect information from stakeholders involved in the small ruminant meat and dairy industries in each partner country.
- Results (across all productions & countries):
 - Tools/ technologies currently on surveyed farms:

Top 3 technologies currently on all surveyed farms:

1. Weigh crate
2. Farm / herd management software
3. Camera / Video Camera

- Tools/technologies deemed most beneficial:

Top 3 technologies that surveyed farmers deemed most beneficial (selected as top 1):

1. Weigh crate
2. Virtual Fences
3. Flock / herd management software

What do we recommend?

- ✓ Improve awareness of the tools and technologies available to small ruminant farmers.
- ✓ Training for farmers wanting to improve their knowledge of the tools and technologies available should be encouraged in future policies.
- ✓ Promote peer to peer knowledge exchange between stakeholders.
- ✓ Develop better after-sales support and regularly update guidance materials.
- ✓ Encourage local policy makers to provide financial support for equipment purchases/sharing.